

DOI:10.5281/zenodo.13988703

Elections, Political Alienation And The Language Of Politics In Nigeria’s Presidential Election: Impact Assessment Of 2015, 2019 And 2023 Elections, South-South, Zone

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ABSTRACT

This research will focus on the 2015, 2019 and 2023 presidential election in Nigeria, using Edo, Delta, and Bayelsa State as a template. The reason for this research is to unravel the trends in the voting pattern of electorates from 2015 to 2023, the factors that influence votes, such as the issues of money politics, vote buying, poverty, and the language of politics and their influence on the electorates since 1999 when Nigeria’s fourth republic started, Nigerian have not enjoyed the dividends of democracy, one of the reasons for this is that the elected leaders have not been able to proffer solution to the problems of underdevelopment and moreover the process in which these leaders assume power is fraudulent and lack transparency. After 23 years of uninterrupted democracy, poverty has pervaded the entire Nigerian state. The concept of political alienation will be examined to ascertain at what stage are the electorates alienated or incorporated and how language is used as a veritable tool in the political system at various stages, in order to ascertain if elections can be judged to be fair, credible, as it represents the will of the people. It is only when the will of the people prevails that democracy can be consolidated.

Keywords: Presidential elections, politics, electorates, political alienation, political language

INTRODUCTION

The Clifford constitution of 1922 is a watershed in the evolution of elections and electoral process in Nigeria. It introduced electoral principles into Nigeria’s politics and administration. The process of electoral democracy in Nigeria has not been perfect since the nation got her political independence from Britain in 1960. Nigeria has organized nine general elections as well as numerous regional, state, and local government elections. These three elections were conducted under the military regimes of 1979, 1983 and 1999 to give room for a transition to civil rule or democratic rule (Agbaje and Adejumobi, 2006). While the other elections were conducted by the civilian government in 1964, 2003, 2007, 2011, 2015 and 2019. In all these elections, especially that of the fourth republic have been fraught with a lot of electoral irregularities and these has made citizens to be skeptical on the ability of the state to conduct free, fair, and credible elections that will allow for free participation by the citizens.

The struggle for democracy in Nigeria was not conceived as an end in itself to military rule, it is also a means to enthrone an accountable political institution that promote good governance and accountability by the government in power (Bello, 2011). In 1999 the population of Nigeria was estimated to be 188.3million (m), out of this figure the voting age population was 52.8m, the number of registered voters was 57.9m, and the total votes cast was 30.3m which is about 52.3 percent. In the year 2003, the estimated population of Nigeria was declared to be 129.9m, and the voting age population was 64.3m, the registered number of voters was also 60.8m and the total vote cast was 69.1 percent.

Similarly, in 2007 the total population of Nigeria was estimated at 131.9m (2006 population census) out of these numbers, the voting age population was 71.0m while the registered voters were 61.6m, and the total vote cast at 35.4m which is about 57.5 percent. And in 2011, the estimated population for Nigeria was 155.2m and the voting age population was 81.7. The total number of registered voters were 73.5m while the total vote cast was 39.5m, totally about 53.7 percent (IDEA, 2016).

There are so many factors that could be responsible for the low turnout of eligible voters, who are duly registered but might fail to cast their votes, this could be due to fear and apathy on the part of electorates, i.e., the fear of their votes not counting, electoral violence, insurgency, hate speeches and intimidating political languages. These are among the factors that likely determine the turnout of electorates to cast their ballots, hence this research seeks to find out if the Nigerian democracy can be consolidated with the needed dividends of democracy derivable.

Problem Statement / Justification

Election is the cardinal principle that gives direction to any democratic process anywhere in the world. It is the defining variable in the process of democratic consolidation. But as it is in Nigeria toady, elections have become war and many unwholesome practices have characterised our democratic processes. Beginning from 1999, with Nigeria's fourth republic, some of the practices includes public statements, abusive languages, hate speeches, electoral violence, ballot snatching, money politics, vote buying and selling, perhaps the general poverty level of most electorates have become tools of manipulation by politicians. Moreover, there have been challenges to access permanent voters' card by electorates, it takes months if not years to be issued permanent voters' cards by the electoral body. The majority of the electorates are skeptical about Nigeria's democracy, hence, the low desire to vote among citizens. Furthermore, there have been a slow growth in the dividends of democracy since 1999. There is need to strengthen our electoral process, so that the votes of the electorates can count and bring in the needed leadership that will transform lives of Nigerians and usher the needed development. As long as politicians aware that the reaction of the electorates will determine the outcome of the polls, they will strive as much as possible to deliver on their electoral promises.

Definition of Terms and Concepts

Election

According to Ojo (2008), election is a process in which persons are chosen to occupy political or some positions of authority (Ojo, 2008). Election is a formal expression of individual preferences by the electorates, which they crystallize into a collective action in the determination of who occupy or do not occupy an office. Nohlen (1996) sees election as a liberal democracy where individuals have the freewill to exercise their franchise and it is a necessary aspect of the democratic process. Lindbergh (2004) sees election as a process whereby representation in any political office is necessitation by periodic elections. Election is seen as the core of democratic practice and process. (See Bratton, 1998; Chiroro, 2005; Ojo, 2007; Nwolise, 2007, and Laakso, 2007).

Political Alienation

Alienation is a function of subnational specific relations between individuals and the society in the process of history; situations such as structural condition or the structure of the society and the individuals in the society (Twinning, 1980). Alienation means aloofness, estrangement, apathy, turning or keeping away, indifference, cutting off something or somebody whether in society, religion, administration, even the self (Johari, 2012:437). Alienation could persist in every facet of the society, it could exist in the economic sphere, in philosophy, in psychology in sociology, in economics, and in politics.

Political alienation, therefore, involves the whole gamut of the electoral process from the beginning to the end and thereby reinforcing the whole process of political alienation from one generation to the other Ohiorenuan and Omosefe, (2020:5). The electoral process begins with the formation of political parties, political campaign, and the actual voting by the electorates. It is the Independent National Electoral Commission (INEC) that is responsible for the conduct of elections in Nigeria. The voting process, the emergence of the actual winner or candidate and the electorate can also be alienated in the policy process from the formulation stage to the implementation of the policies, which further reinforces the process of alienation from one stage to another in the process of political development. (Ohiorenuan and Omosefe, 2020:5).

Alienation signifies meaninglessness, powerlessness, normlessness, isolation, and self-estrangement and this brings about disaffection with the present political system. (Johari, 2012:441). Powerless could be seen as the inability of the people, the electorates to influence the decision of the authoritative decision makers in the allocation of values or utilities. Political meaninglessness could exist when the decisions of the authoritative decision makers are unpredictable. This kind of alienation exist when individuals are not able to distinguish any meaningful political choices and the outcomes of such choices are not easily predictable. For example, electorates vote for certain candidates, but because sometimes their candidates are not the eventual winners of such election due to some electoral malpractices and this could lead to further alienation by affecting their response to subsequent elections.

Political isolation or alienation could exist when individuals in the society have a feeling that certain norms that guide political activities are not upheld by political actors, especially when they feel that the rules are double standard or unfair and there are illegitimate actions, that is at variance with the laid down principles, political self-estrangement could also exist when individuals are used as pawns at different levels in the society, for example, the voter could see him or herself as a commodity that could be priced by political office holders to achieve their ends without actually involved in the process of political decision making. After every four years, the politicians come with money to get their votes, without necessary gaining the dividends of democracy. (Ohiorenuan and Osaigbovo, 2020).

Fig. I: Electoral process

Source: Ohiorenuan and Omosefe, (2020)

At every stage in the diagram above, the electorates can be alienated.

Stage I:

This is the stage where the Independent National Electoral Commission (INEC), and the political parties carry out political campaigns and voter sensitization on the need to vote and how to vote. The political sensitization stage is the stage where the INEC carry out voter enlightenment on how to vote, making sure that the people are focus how to vote, and what makes their vote void and how to ensure that they make their votes count by putting their fingers on the right box for their preferred candidate. The political parties also carry out political campaigns, telling the people or the electorates what they have for them when they are voted into power, some who have party manifestoes present it to the electorate in this stage.

Stage II:

At this stage, the electorates are registered in preparation for the voting period. This stage is solely the responsibility of the independent national electoral commission. They register candidates or electorates who are eighteen years and above. But the major challenge at this stage is that the people can be on the cue for hours because of lack of functional electronic machines or inadequate machines; by doing so, they get discouraged to participate.

Stage III:

This is the stage where the electorates and INEC carry out accreditation of voters and the electorate vote for their preferred candidates. This is the stage where voters are accredited by the independent national electoral commission on the voting day before they are allowed to vote. But what has been noticed in the 2015 general election is that people are accredited, and they go home, and some may never come back, but the rule was changed in 2019 general election, once you are accredited, you go and vote, there is no need to go and come back again.

Stage IV:

This is the last stage which either determines the level of alienation of the electorate or participation. The legitimacy by performance goes a long way to determine the trust of the electorate on the government and future elections. In an enlightened populace, the questions they ask are these: have the previous policies effected our lives, have they delivered on campaign promises, how many people have been lifted out of poverty line? This is the final stage of the voting process; this is where the elected candidates are given certificate of return and sworn into office for four years according to the constitutional provision. This is where the people are alienated in terms of electoral promises or the dividends of democracy, more often than not promises are not kept by the politicians to the people, the social contract of providing the greatest number of happiness to the majority of the people is not adhered to and as such there is a lot of cynicism on the part of the electorate. The will and the zeal to come out and vote is not there because of the previous cumulative negative experience they have had over the years of broken promises. On this issue, the elected officers lack legitimacy in terms of performance in office.

Furthermore, alienation as a concept has three major approaches to the problematic and the meaning. The first approach sees alienation as a psychological phenomenon, the second approach stratified the social sources of alienation and the third approach which relates to political alienation is about narrowing the field of inquiry, which the particular objects from which individuals are alienated, the examination of the individual perception of alienation. The reasons for these objects of alienation are above the implication for the political system. (Kon, 1967)

In this approach the concept of political alienation relates to individuals' attitude towards political world, an appraisal of those attitudes to the political system. It comprises various forms of estrangement from political structures, political processes, and subjective evaluation of the individual in the process of political leadership. It may also mean estrangement from the dominant values of the political system. This kind of alienation is important because for the system to maintain equilibrium and stability it depends partly upon the legitimacy and the consensus of the generality of the people in the political pursuit (Dahl, 1965:133). Those who pay allegiance to the political process see it as legitimate because there is a convergence of the values of the political leadership and the followership (Lane, 1962: 162).

Political alienation involves the process of acceptance or rejection of the norms that guides political action or behavior. This form of alienation from the societal norms and values are described by Durkheim (1951: 257) as anomic which is a state of normlessness in the political system. Merton,

(1957:121-194) refers to anomie as a social situation where there is a dislocation between cultural goals and prescribed means to achieve the stated goals.

In addition to normlessness the concept of political alienation may relate to individual's perception about political structures and organisations. It may relate to individual's perception about the output structures, such as legislature, judiciary, and executive, as well as the input structures such as political parties, interest group, political leadership, and the evaluation of the individual as a participant in the political process. Some persons may be alienated from the output structures, but not the input structures and vice versa.

Political alienation has also been examined in terms of an individual's evaluation of his personal political role or sense of political efficacy. Thus, those who feel politically powerless believe that their actions cannot determine political outcomes. Discussions of this aspect of political alienation in the literature Centre on 'alienation from roles' and 'alienation from facilities', where facilities refer to the means available to influence political outcomes. In the literature these are identified as powerlessness and meaninglessness. Seeman, for example, defines powerlessness as:

The expectancy or probability held by the individual that his own behaviour cannot determine the occurrence of the outcomes, or reinforcements he seeks.

He found this conception to be central to Marx's discussion of alienation and to a certain extent in Max Weber's discussion of bureaucracy. Angus Campbell's understanding of personal effectiveness closely approaches Seeman's concept of powerlessness. Campbell assumes that:

People begin at an early age to develop a sense of their own capacity to manage the world around them. We think that some people develop a self-confident, positive attitude with which they meet the problems of everyday life while others see themselves as characteristically giving way in the face of environmental pressure unable to manage the conflicting forces which they encounter.

Meaninglessness, on the other hand, is defined by Seeman as a state in which the individual feels "unclear as to what he ought to believe-when the individual's minimal standards for clarity in decision-making are not met." Since political knowledge is a major tool or political facility essential to political participation, the belief that political information is either absent or purposely confusing induces meaninglessness and the consequent alienation from the political process.

Many writers view powerlessness and meaninglessness as synonymous with alienation but this is a fallacy since the alienated need not necessarily feel powerless. The politically alienated may differ in their appraisals of the existing political order, in the degree of their dissatisfaction with the political process, and in terms of their belief in the possibility or necessity of producing political change through either legitimate or illegitimate channels but this is not necessarily powerlessness. Estrangement or alienation from the political system may involve one or several of the components of social action as identified by Smelser (Koener, 1968). He says Koener claims that:

Disagreement with particular political policies does not necessarily constitute political alienation unless this disagreement is such that it translates into alienation from values, norms, roles, or facilities which are the components of social action.

However, Almond and Verba (1963:14,15) disagrees with the above comment that those who disagree with policy are alienated, but rather they constitute a policy sub-culture that are not constantly directed towards policy input and outputs which are always in allegiance to the political structure. Participation in political activities and the political systems is directly linked to general social participation of individuals in the affairs of the state, at the community, village, local government, state, and national levels.

There are a number of ways in which individuals can participate in politics. These include voting, working in elections, making financial contributions to political parties, petitioning, and writing letters to public officials, reading about politics, viewing, or listening to political broadcasts, engaging in discussion about politics, and holding memberships in political organisations (Lane, 1959). Some of these modes of participation are identical with formal social participation as discussed earlier but much of political participation is informal in character and thus more difficult to assess.

For the most part, political participation does not differ significantly from general social participation in respect to the descriptive characteristics studied. Here too, social-economic status appears to be most significant variable influencing all aspects of political participation.

Language of Politics

The use of language is a veritable tool for political activities in Nigeria. These includes the language and words used in identifying various political parties, their logos, slogans, flyers, and political jingles. Political parties and politicians use various forms and means, including languages to mobilise their teaming followers for campaigns. The choice of language they deployed on many occasions could be translated by listeners the way they understand them. And since language convey different meanings to various listeners, there are bound to be linguistic implications and interpretations that hearers could react to in a peaceful or violence manner.

Political language establishes a special relationship that must exist between the speaker (composer) and the audience (the listener). However, the major goal of political language, apart from the normal business of politics, it is meant to persuade the listener, that is members of the party and the public to key into political manifestos. Micheal Angel Folorunso (34:2013) affirms this view about political language when he writes that:

The language we use to communicate as tools for reelection that assist us in thought, reasoning, and problem solving. We usually think of language as a body of words used by a people who agree on what objects those words refer to. So long as there is widespread agreement on the relationship between words and their referents, we have an object language that facilitates the transmission of information.

This assertion by Folorunso clearly addresses the role of language during political activities in society. The choice of language deployed by a group of is capable of influencing their thoughts and actions. For instance, the words that are inscribed in party's moto, as well as the languages they use in their slogans convey symbolic messages. Marietu Tenuche (2009:48) in agreement highlights the power of language employed by candidates during campaigns when he refers to the presidential aspirant of the People's Democratic Party of Nigeria. (PDP):

The President, Obasanjo's political language conveys his perception of politics and electoral competition. The President's most quoted dictum that "this election is a do or die affair for me and the PDP. This election is a matter of life and death for the PDP and Nigeria", depicts his perception of politics and electoral competition as a continuation of warfare by some other means.

Tenuche is apt in the above comment that he ascribes to Obasanjo with such rhetoric that he feels are capable of hitting the polity which might have advert effects on elections. He continues that the language comment used by candidates are revelation of their intention towards such contest.

It is in the same vein Philips O. Okolo and David E. Atiye (2022:253) are precise when they claim that:

The desperation of party politics and political parties in Nigeria to acquire and control political power, has made them resort to all sorts of activities, to include hate speeches campaigns, political violence, moral and immoral act to ensure that political party capture power at all means.

The duo points to the fact that political Parties resort to abusive languages which he terms hate speeches. They link this action to the eagerness and desperation for political power. The choices political languages have far reached implications that may make or mar the electoral processes of any nation.

Overview of Elections in Nigeria

A general election was held in 1964, just after four years of Nigeria's political independence and it was fraught with a lot of electoral malpractices, boycotts by the citizens, and electoral violence (Ademoyega, 1981:56). A large majority of the election as won by the Nigerian National Alliance (NNA), which the United Progressive Grand Alliance (UPGA), did not participate due to this boycott a supplementary election was held in 1965 in the Eastern region and the UPGA won all seats in the region. Due to the violence that occurred the Igbos fled to the East for their safety (Kesselman et al, 2010:371). Due to this widespread violence that emanated from the 1964 election, the military, felt that Nigeria was not ready for the democratic rule (Onwudiwe and Berwind Dart, 2010).

Due to the widespread electoral violence that engulfed the 1964 election, the military struck in January 1966 and this was the first military coup in Nigeria political history and there was a counter coup that same year, the events that followed led to the Nigerian civil war that started in 1967 and

ended in 1970, there was suspension of political parties and political activities, but in 1978 the ban was lifted and the presidential system was adopted.

The second republic witnessed the formation of some major political parties, like Nigeria Peoples Party (NPP), which was formed in the eastern region, in the West there was the Unity Party of Nigeria (UPN). The National Party of Nigeria was also formed and it was the ruling party at that time, there was widespread electoral malpractices by various political parties, the NPN tried to dislodge the NPP led by Dr. Nnamdi Azikiwe, they also tried to remove the governor of the defunct Bendel State, Prof. Folorunso Ambrose Ali, the PRP and NPP lost in Kaduna and Anambra States respectively due to the alleged electoral malpractice by the ruling NPN and this culminated in widespread electoral violence that gave rise to the second coming of the military in 1983 Otoghagua (2007:166).

Subsequent elections led by Ibrahim Badamosi Babangida, Sani Abacha and General Abdulsalami Abubakar was characterised by various forms of electoral violence. The election conducted by Babangida was adjudged to be the freest and fairest in Nigeria's political history, but Babangida annulled the election, and it almost ended the Nigerian state (Onwudiere and Berwind-Dart, 2010). The 1999 general election which was conducted by Abdulsalami Abubakar was hurriedly done and it did not witness much electoral violence as observed by international observers. This was due to the general dissatisfaction of Nigerians with military rule and moreover, the military was ready to deal with any form of electoral violence that could emerge from any part of the country (Onwudiere and Berwind-Dart, 2010).

The 2003 general election was a sharp deviation from the 1999 election, because there was an array of unemployed youths who became tools in the hands of the politicians, the win at all cost syndrome by the politicians led to various inter and intra-party violence that led to the loss of lives and properties, there was already a volatile situation in the Niger Delta area, because of youths yearning for a share in the national cake, they felt that their region was underdeveloped. Youths were hired to serve some selfish political interest, the array of unemployed youths became ready tools in the hands of politician, who exchange their power for monetary benefit Onwudiere and Berwind, (2010:222).

Table 1: Voting patterns in presidential election in Nigeria from 1999-2015

Population	Voting age population	Registered voters	Total votes cast	%
181.6m	2015 (91.7m)	68.8m	29.4m	42.7
155.2m	2011 (81.7m)	73.5m	39.5m	53.7
131.9m	2007 (71.0m)	61.6m	35.4m	57.5
129.9m	2003 (64.3m)	60.8m	42.0m	69.1
108.3m	1999 (52.8m)	57.9m	30.3m	52.3

Source: International Institute for Democracy and Electoral Assistance (IDEA)

The table above shows the population of Nigeria from 1999, to 2015. The second column is the years of election and the voting age population in parenthesis, the third column shows the number of voters in millions and the fourth column shows the total votes cast.

In 1999, the total voting age population is 52.8m, the total number of registered voters is 57.9m and the total vote cast was 30.3m, which means that approximately half of the total population of registered voters did not vote. In 2003, the total number of registered voters was 60.8m and the total vote cast was 42.0m, which means there is a short fall of about 18 million registered voters who did not vote.

In 2007, the total number of registered voters was 61.6m and the total vote cast was 35.4m, which means there is a difference of over 25m persons who did not cast their vote. In 2011, there was 73.5m registered voters and the total vote cast was 39.5m population, with a difference of over 32 million persons who did not cast their votes. In 2015, there was 68.8m registered voters out of that number only 29.4m persons cast their vote, which means over 37m persons did not cast their votes. The total number of registered voters for the five years put together is 322.6m registered voters with a total vote cast of 176.6. The implication is that about 146m persons did not cast their votes despite being registered to vote.

METHODOLOGY

Mixed method will be adopted in this research (Creswell, 2009). The reasons are that we are going to examine the voting part term from 2015 to date, in terms of how many were alienated as the problems encountered in the elections. The primary or secondary method will also be adopted to ascertain the present situation on ground, by administering questionnaire to residents to some local government in the three states, Edo, Delta, and Bayelsa States.

Population and Sample: 500 persons will be chosen from two Local Government each with the proportional stratified sampling method in Edo, Delta and Bayelsa which makes it 3,000 sample size.

Instruments of Data Collection and Analysis: In this research we will adopt the Likert scale of measurement and it will contain five questions for each objective that will make it 30 questions and moreover, 5 questions will be drawn to interview some stakeholders in these states.

Method of Data Analysis: The quantitative data developed from the field or questionnaires returned as well as responses from the interview conducted would be analysed by using both descriptive and inferential statistics. The descriptive statistics will include the use of frequency distribution tables and simple percentages. The inferential statistics will be used to explain the nature of the relationship existing between the independent and dependent variables. In order to tackle the problems raised in the objective section, the data would be analysed by using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS).

RESULT AND FINDINGS

The results of this study are presented below in accordance with the stated research questions and the formulated hypotheses in the study.

Research Question One

What is the Reason for Electoral Violence in South-South Geopolitical Zone of Nigeria?

Table I:

Descriptive Statistical Analysis on the Reason for Electoral Violence in South-South Geopolitical Zone of Nigeria

Statements	Responses					
	Agreed		Disagreed		Total Freq.	Total %
	Freq.	%	Freq.	%		
The win at all cost syndrome leads to electoral violence	3000	100.00	-	-	3000	100.00
Seeing politics as the only means to livelihood leads to electoral violence	2500	83.4	500	16.6	3000	100.00
The sit-tight syndrome of our leaders leads to electoral violence	2500	83.4	500	16.6	3000	100.00
The use of security operative and INEC officials to rig elections could lead to electoral violence	2600	86.7	400	13.3	3000	100.00

Results in Table I above revealed the descriptive statistical analysis on the Reason for Electoral Violence in South-South Geopolitical Zone of Nigeria. Results show that of the 3000 respondents, 3000 representing 100.0% of the respondents agreed that ‘the win at all cost syndrome leads to electoral violence’ in South-South Geopolitical Zone of Nigeria. While none of the respondents disagreed to the statement. Two thousand five hundred (2500) of them representing 83.4% of the respondents agreed that ‘Seeing politics as the only means to livelihood leads to electoral violence’ in South-South Geopolitical Zone of Nigeria. and 500 of the respondents representing 16.6% of the respondents disagreed. On the statement ‘The sit-tight syndrome of our leaders leads to electoral violence, 2500 representing 83.4% of the respondents agreed. While 500 of them representing 16.6% of the respondents disagreed. Results also revealed that 2600 respondents, representing 86.7% agreed that ‘the use of security operative and INEC officials to rig elections could lead to electoral violence’ in South-South Geopolitical Zone of Nigeria. while 400 respondents, representing 13.3% disagreed to the statement.

Hypotheses Testing

Hypothesis One:

There is no significant difference in the opinion of the respondents that, the win at all cost syndrome leads to electoral violence, seeing politics as the only means to livelihood leads to electoral violence, the sit-tight syndrome of our leaders leads to electoral violence and the use of security operative and INEC officials to rig elections could lead to electoral violence is the Reason for Electoral Violence in South-South Geopolitical Zone of Nigeria.

Table 2

Friedman Test of Significant on the opinion of the respondents that, on the Reason for Electoral Violence in South-South Geopolitical Zone of Nigeria.

S/N	Statements	N	Mean	SD	Mean Rank	Df	χ^2	P-value
1.	The win at all cost syndrome leads to electoral violence	3000	1.6333	0.48197	2.22	3	355.738	0.000
2.	Seeing politics as the only means to livelihood leads to electoral violence	3000	1.9333	0.72737	2.65			
3.	The sit-tight syndrome of our leaders leads to electoral violence	3000	1.8333	0.77830	2.50			
4.	The use of security operative and INEC officials to rig elections could lead to electoral violence	3000	1.8667	0.61834	2.63			

***Alpha (α) = 0.05 level of significance**

Results in the above table revealed that the Friedman test of Significant on the reason for Electoral Violence in South-South Geopolitical Zone of Nigeria. The results showed a computed chi-square (χ^2) value of 355.738, testing at 0.05 alpha (α) level of significance with a degree of freedom (df) of 3, P-value of 0.000. Since the P-value (0.000) is less than the alpha level of significance (0.05), the hypothesis which state that ‘there is no significant difference in the opinion of the respondents that, the win at all cost syndrome leads to electoral violence, seeing politics as the only means to livelihood leads to electoral violence, the sit-tight syndrome of our leaders leads to electoral violence and the use of security operative and INEC officials to rig elections could lead to electoral violence is the Reason for Electoral Violence in South-South Geopolitical Zone of Nigeria’ was rejected at $P < 0.05$ alpha (α) level of significance. Conclusion is therefore reached that there is a significant difference in the opinion of the respondents that, the win at all cost syndrome leads to electoral violence, seeing politics as the only means to livelihood leads to electoral violence, the sit-tight syndrome of our leaders leads to electoral violence and the use of security operative and INEC officials to rig elections could lead to electoral violence is the Reason for Electoral Violence in South-South Geopolitical Zone of Nigeria.

Frequencies

Frequency Table

GENDER OF RESPONDENTS

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	MALE	2200	73.3	73.3	73.3
	FEMALE	800	26.7	26.7	100.0
	Total	3000	100.0	100.0	

AGE OF RESPONDENTS

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid 18-25	100	3.3	3.3	3.3
26-35	900	30.0	30.0	33.3
36-45	1100	36.7	36.7	70.0
46-55	900	30.0	30.0	100.0
Total	3000	100.0	100.0	

QUALIFICATION OF RESPONDENT

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid SSCE/GCE	100	3.3	3.3	3.3
ND/NCE	100	3.3	3.3	6.7
HND/B.SC	2100	70.0	70.0	76.7
M.SC	700	23.3	23.3	100.0
Total	3000	100.0	100.0	

MARITAL STATUS OF RESPONDENT

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid MARRIED	2100	70.0	70.0	70.0
SINGLE	800	26.7	26.7	96.7
SEPARATED	100	3.3	3.3	100.0
Total	3000	100.0	100.0	

The win at all cost syndrome leads to electoral violence

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid AGREED	1100	36.7	36.7	36.7
STRONGLY AGREED	1900	63.3	63.3	100.0
Total	3000	100.0	100.0	

Seeing politics as the only means to livelihood leads to electoral violence

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid AGREED	800	26.7	26.7	26.7
STRONGLY AGREED	1700	56.7	56.7	83.3
DISAGREED	400	13.3	13.3	96.7
STRONGLY DISAGREED	100	3.3	3.3	100.0
Total	3000	100.0	100.0	

The sit-tight syndrome of our leaders leads to electoral violence

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid AGREED	1100	36.7	36.7	36.7
STRONGLY AGREED	1400	46.7	46.7	83.3
DISAGREED	400	13.3	13.3	96.7
STRONGLY DISAGREED	100	3.3	3.3	100.0
Total	3000	100.0	100.0	

The use of security operative an INEC officials to rig elections could lead to electoral violence

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid AGREED	800	26.7	26.7	26.7
STRONGLY AGREED	1800	60.0	60.0	86.7
DISAGREED	400	13.3	13.3	100.0
Total	3000	100.0	100.0	

The inability of electorates to get their voters card could lead to alienation

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	AGREED	1500	50.0	50.0	50.0
	STRONGLY AGREED	1300	43.3	43.3	93.3
	STRONGLY DISAGREED	200	6.7	6.7	100.0
	Total	3000	100.0	100.0	

The inability of electorates to be registered could lead to alienation

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	AGREED	1400	46.7	46.7	46.7
	STRONGLY AGREED	1200	40.0	40.0	86.7
	DISAGREED	400	13.3	13.3	100.0
	Total	3000	100.0	100.0	

Insecurity in the polling unit could lead to non-participation of electorates and alienation

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	AGREED	800	26.7	26.7	26.7
	STRONGLY AGREED	1800	60.0	60.0	86.7
	DISAGREED	400	13.3	13.3	100.0
	Total	3000	100.0	100.0	

The Naira redesign policy of the federal Government led to cash strap and inability of electorates to access transportation to their polling units.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	AGREED	900	30.0	30.0	30.0
	STRONGLY AGREED	1400	46.7	46.7	76.7
	DISAGREED	400	13.3	13.3	90.0
	STRONGLY DISAGREED	300	10.0	10.0	100.0
	Total	3000	100.0	100.0	

Fuel scarcity led to voters alienation in the 2023 presidential election

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	AGREED	1700	56.7	56.7	56.7
	STRONGLY AGREED	600	20.0	20.0	76.7
	DISAGREED	700	23.3	23.3	100.0
	Total	3000	100.0	100.0	

The absence of the dividends of democracy does not make electorates to have faith in the democratic process

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	AGREED	1090	36.3	36.8	36.8
	STRONGLY AGREED	849	28.3	28.7	65.5
	DISAGREED	1023	34.1	34.5	100.0
	Total	2962	98.7	100.0	
Missing	System	38	1.3		
Total		3000	100.0		

The feeling that our votes does not count do not make electorates to have faith in our democratic process

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	AGREED	1100	36.7	36.7	36.7

STRONGLY AGREED	1600	53.3	53.3	90.0
DISAGREED	200	6.7	6.7	96.7
STRONGLY DISAGREED	100	3.3	3.3	100.0
Total	3000	100.0	100.0	

The lack of credible political options does not make electorates to have faith in our democratic process.

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid AGREED	1490	49.7	49.7	49.7
STRONGLY AGREED	1010	33.7	33.7	83.3
DISAGREED	500	16.7	16.7	100.0
Total	3000	100.0	100.0	

Politicians seeing politics as a means of amassing wealth

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid AGREED	500	16.7	16.7	16.7
STRONGLY AGREED	2300	76.7	76.7	93.3
DISAGREED	100	3.3	3.3	96.7
STRONGLY DISAGREED	100	3.3	3.3	100.0
Total	3000	100.0	100.0	

The process of emergence of the candidate of a political party leads to money politics

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid AGREED	1400	46.7	46.7	46.7
STRONGLY AGREED	1400	46.7	46.7	93.3
DISAGREED	200	6.7	6.7	100.0
Total	3000	100.0	100.0	

Political elites forming/funding political parties as investment leads to money politics

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid AGREED	1200	40.0	40.0	40.0
STRONGLY AGREED	1600	53.3	53.3	93.3
DISAGREED	200	6.7	6.7	100.0
Total	3000	100.0	100.0	

The poverty of electorate makes them susceptible to manipulation by the politicians

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid AGREED	1002	33.4	33.4	33.4
STRONGLY AGREED	1658	55.3	55.3	88.7
DISAGREED	140	4.7	4.7	93.3
STRONGLY DISAGREED	200	6.7	6.7	100.0
Total	3000	100.0	100.0	

The lack of access of most electorates to information (television, radio and newspapers) makes them unaware of political events

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid AGREED	1011	33.7	33.7	33.7
STRONGLY AGREED	1359	45.3	45.3	79.0
DISAGREED	430	14.3	14.3	93.3
STRONGLY DISAGREED	200	6.7	6.7	100.0
Total	3000	100.0	100.0	

Increasing the numbers of registration centers can reduce stress in registration and collections of PVCs

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	AGREED	1502	50.1	50.1	50.1
	STRONGLY AGREED	1170	39.0	39.0	89.1
	DISAGREED	328	10.9	10.9	100.0
	Total	3000	100.0	100.0	

Availability of functional registration machine will reduce stress in registration and collection of voters cards.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	AGREED	1202	40.1	40.1	40.1
	STRONGLY AGREED	1759	58.6	58.6	98.7
	DISAGREED	30	1.0	1.0	99.7
	STRONGLY DISAGREED	9	.3	.3	100.0
	Total	3000	100.0	100.0	

Having well trained technical staffs to operate the voters registration machines will reduce stress in registration and collection of PVCs

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	AGREED	1202	40.1	40.1	40.1
	STRONGLY AGREED	1479	49.3	49.3	89.4
	DISAGREED	319	10.6	10.6	100.0
	Total	3000	100.0	100.0	

The guarantee that votes will count as a result of the usage of BVAS and IREV will increases voters participation

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	AGREED	1202	40.1	40.1	40.1
	STRONGLY AGREED	1779	59.3	59.3	99.4
	DISAGREED	19	.6	.6	100.0
	Total	3000	100.0	100.0	

The introduction of BIVAS and IREV discouraged ballot snatching

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	AGREED	1902	63.4	63.4	63.4
	STRONGLY AGREED	977	32.6	32.6	96.0
	DISAGREED	21	.7	.7	96.7
	STRONGLY DISAGREED	100	3.3	3.3	100.0
	Total	3000	100.0	100.0	

The use of BIVAS and IREV reduces electoral violence in Nigeria

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	AGREED	1302	43.4	43.4	43.4
	STRONGLY AGREED	1088	36.3	36.3	79.7
	DISAGREED	310	10.3	10.3	90.0
	STRONGLY DISAGREED	300	10.0	10.0	100.0
	Total	3000	100.0	100.0	

By making INEC truly independent not in name but in practice, Nigerians can get dividends of democracy

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid AGREED	1102	36.7	36.7	36.7
STRONGLY AGREED	1188	39.6	39.6	76.3
DISAGREED	510	17.0	17.0	93.3
STRONGLY DISAGREED	200	6.7	6.7	100.0
Total	3000	100.0	100.0	

By ensuring that the votes of the electorates truly counts , there can be the dividends of democracy

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid AGREED	902	30.1	30.1	30.1
STRONGLY AGREED	1888	62.9	62.9	93.0
DISAGREED	210	7.0	7.0	100.0
Total	3000	100.0	100.0	

By making the electorates to participate in policy process will ensure the dividends of democracy

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid AGREED	1302	43.4	43.4	43.4
STRONGLY AGREED	1388	46.3	46.3	89.7
DISAGREED	310	10.3	10.3	100.0
Total	3000	100.0	100.0	

Hate speech should be resisted by political parties and same be entrenched in the electoral acts

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid AGREED	1302	43.4	43.4	43.4
STRONGLY AGREED	1188	39.6	39.6	83.0
DISAGREED	510	17.0	17.0	100.0
Total	3000	100.0	100.0	

Some political parties deploy propaganda as a means and rivalry devices during campaigns

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid AGREED	1702	56.7	56.7	56.7
STRONGLY AGREED	1188	39.6	39.6	96.3
DISAGREED	110	3.7	3.7	100.0
Total	3000	100.0	100.0	

An intense magnitude of threatening languages before and during elections are capable of scaring away the electorates from the polling boots.

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid AGREED	1302	43.4	43.4	43.4
STRONGLY AGREED	1488	49.6	49.6	93.0
DISAGREED	210	7.0	7.0	100.0
Total	3000	100.0	100.0	

The ability of electoral body to set up monitoring committee in clamping down on politicians indulging in threatening languages must be nib at the bud

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid AGREED	1502	50.1	50.1	50.1
STRONGLY AGREED	1288	42.9	42.9	93.0
DISAGREED	210	7.0	7.0	100.0
Total	3000	100.0	100.0	

By ensuring that adequate penalty by INEC are imposed on political parties indulging in the use of hate speeches may also check election violence.

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid AGREED	1302	43.4	43.4	43.4
STRONGLY AGREED	1288	42.9	42.9	86.3
DISAGREED	410	13.7	13.7	100.0
Total	3000	100.0	100.0	

Friedman Test

Descriptive Statistics

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Minimum	Maximum
The win at all cost syndrome leads to electoral violence	3000	1.6333	.48197	1.00	2.00
Seeing politics as the only means to livelihood leads to electoral violence	3000	1.9333	.72737	1.00	4.00
The sit-tight syndrome of our leaders leads to electoral violence	3000	1.8333	.77830	1.00	4.00
The use of security operative an INEC officials to rig elections could lead to electoral violence	3000	1.8667	.61834	1.00	3.00

Friedman Test

Ranks

	Mean Rank
The win at all cost syndrome leads to electoral violence	2.22
Seeing politics as the only means to livelihood leads to electoral violence	2.65
The sit-tight syndrome of our leaders leads to electoral violence	2.50
The use of security operative an INEC officials to rig elections could lead to electoral violence	2.63

Test Statistics

N	3000
Chi-Square	355.738
df	3
Asymp. Sig.	.000

a. Friedman Test

NPAR TESTS/FRIEDMAN=ITEM5 ITEM6 ITEM7 ITEM8
ITEM9 /STATISTICS DESCRIPTIVES /MISSING LISTWISE.

Descriptive Statistics

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Minimum	Maximum
The inability of electorates to get their voters card could lead to alienation	3000	1.6333	.79526	1.00	4.00
The inability of electorates to be registered could lead to alienation	3000	1.6667	.69932	1.00	3.00
Insecurity in the polling unit could lead to non-participation of electorates and alienation	3000	1.8667	.61834	1.00	3.00
The Naira redesign policy of the federal Government led to cash strap and inability of electorates to access transportation to their polling units.	3000	2.0333	.91241	1.00	4.00
Fuel scarcity led to voters alienation in the 2023 presidential election	3000	1.6667	.83013	1.00	3.00

Friedman Test

Ranks

	Mean Rank
The inability of electorates to get their voters card could lead to alienation	2.85
The inability of electorates to be registered could lead to alienation	2.87
Insecurity in the polling unit could lead to non-participation of electorates and alienation	3.17
The Naira redesign policy of the federal Government led to cash strap and inability of electorates to access transportation to their polling units.	3.40
Fuel scarcity led to voters alienation in the 2023 presidential election	2.72

Test Statistics^a

N	3000
Chi-Square	628.895
Df	4
Asymp. Sig.	.000

a. Friedman Test

NPAR TESTS/FRIEDMAN=ITEM10 ITEM11 ITEM12
/STATISTICS DESCRIPTIVES

Descriptive Statistics

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Minimum	Maximum
The absence of the dividends of democracy does not make electorates to have faith in the democratic process	2962	1.9774	.84445	1.00	3.00
The feeling that our votes does not count do not make electorates to have faith in our democratic process	2962	1.7380	.67390	1.00	4.00
The lack of credible political options does not make electorates to have faith in our democratic process.	2962	1.6529	.73399	1.00	3.00

Friedman Test

Ranks

	Mean Rank
The absence of the dividends of democracy does not make electorates to have faith in the democratic process	2.15
The feeling that our votes does not count do not make electorates to have faith in our democratic process	2.07
The lack of credible political options does not make electorates to have faith in our democratic process.	1.78

Test Statistics

N	2962
Chi-Square	387.915
df	2
Asymp. Sig.	.000

a. Friedman Test

NPAR TESTS /FRIEDMAN=ITEM13 ITEM14
ITEM15 /STATISTICS DESCRIPTIVES /MISSING LISTWISE.

Descriptive Statistics

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Minimum	Maximum
Politicians seeing politics as a means of amassing wealth	3000	1.9333	.57358	1.00	4.00
The process of emergence of the candidate of a political party leads to money politics	3000	1.6000	.61111	1.00	3.00

Political elites forming/funding political parties as investment leads to money politics	3000	1.6667	.59638	1.00	3.00
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Friedman Test

Ranks

	Mean Rank
Politicians seeing politics as a means of amassing wealth	2.27
The process of emergence of the candidate of a political party leads to money politics	1.83
Political elites forming/funding political parties as investment leads to money politics	1.90

Test Statistics

N	3000
Chi-Square	753.846
df	2
Asymp. Sig.	.000

a. Friedman Test

NPAR TESTS/FRIEDMAN=ITEM16
ITEM17 /STATISTICS DESCRIPTIVES
/MISSING LISTWISE.

Descriptive Statistics

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Minimum	Maximum
The poverty of electorate makes them susceptible to manipulation by the politicians	3000	1.8460	.78983	1.00	4.00
The lack of access of most electorates to information (television, radio and newspapers) makes them unaware of political events	3000	1.9397	.86233	1.00	4.00

Friedman Test

Ranks

	Mean Rank
The poverty of electorate makes them susceptible to manipulation by the politicians	1.45
The lack of access of most electorates to information (television, radio and newspapers) makes them unaware of political events	1.55

Test Statistics^a

N	3000
Chi-Square	45.934
Df	1
Asymp. Sig.	.000

a. Friedman Test

NPAR TESTS/CHISQUARE=ITEM16
ITEM17 /EXPECTED=EQUAL/STATISTICS DESCRIPTIVES
/MISSING ANALYSIS.

Descriptive Statistics

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Minimum	Maximum
Increasing the numbers of registration centers can reduce stress in registration and collections of PVCs	3000	1.6087	.67603	1.00	3.00

Availability of functional registration machine will reduce stress in registration and collection of voters cards.	3000	1.6153	.52420	1.00	4.00
Having well trained technical staffs to operate the voters registration machines will reduce stress in registration and collection of PVCs	3000	1.7057	.64847	1.00	3.00

Friedman Test

Ranks

	Mean Rank
Increasing the numbers of registration centers can reduce stress in registration and collections of PVCs	1.95
Availability of functional registration machine will reduce stress in registration and collection of voters cards.	2.01
Having well trained technical staffs to operate the voters registration machines will reduce stress in registration and collection of PVCs	2.05

Test Statistics^a

N	3000
Chi-Square	37.593
Df	2
Asymp. Sig.	.000

a. Friedman Test

NPAR TESTS /FRIEDMAN=ITEM21 ITEM22
ITEM23 /STATISTICS DESCRIPTIVES /MISSING LISTWISE.

Descriptive Statistics

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Minimum	Maximum
The guarantee that votes will count as a result of usage of BVAS and IREV increases voter's participation	3000	1.6057	.50158	1.00	3.00
The introduction of BIVAS and IREV discouraged ballot snatching	3000	1.4397	.67861	1.00	4.00
The use of BIVAS and IREV reduces electoral violence in Nigeria	3000	1.8693	.95946	1.00	4.00

Friedman Test

Ranks

	Mean Rank
The guarantee that votes will count as a result of usage of BVAS and IREV increases voters participation	2.07
The introduction of BIVAS and IREV discouraged ballot snatching	1.79
The use of BIVAS and IREV reduces electoral violence in Nigeria	2.15

Test Statistics^a

N	3000
Chi-Square	493.616
Df	2
Asymp. Sig.	.000

a. Friedman Test

NPAR TESTS/FRIEDMAN=ITEM24 ITEM25 ITEM26
/STATISTICS DESCRIPTIVES/MISSING LISTWISE.

Descriptive Statistics

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Minimum	Maximum
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By making INEC truly independent not in name but in practice, Nigerians can get dividends of democracy	3000	1.9360	.89452	1.00	4.00
By ensuring that the votes of the electorates truly counts , we can have the dividends of democracy	3000	1.7693	.56353	1.00	3.00
By making the electorates to participate in policy process will ensure the dividends of democracy	3000	1.6693	.65432	1.00	3.00

Friedman Test

Ranks

	Mean Rank
By making INEC truly independent not in name but in practice, Nigerians can get dividends of democracy	2.10
By ensuring that the votes of the electorates truly counts , we can have the dividends of democracy	2.02
By making the electorates to participate in policy process will ensure the dividends of democracy	1.88

Test Statistics^a

N	3000
Chi-Square	150.877
Df	2
Asymp. Sig.	.000

a. Friedman Test

NPART TESTS /FRIEDMAN=ITEM27 ITEM28 ITEM29 ITEM30 ITEM31
/STATISTICS DESCRIPTIVES /MISSING LISTWISE.

	N	Mean			
Hate speech should be resisted by political parties and same be entrenched in the electoral acts	3000	1.7360			
Some political parties deploy propaganda as a means and rivalry devices during campaigns	3000	1.4693			
An intense magnitude of threatening languages before and during elections are capable of scaring away the electorates from the polling boots.	3000	1.6360	.60961	3.00	Descriptive Statistics
The ability of electoral body to set up monitoring committee in clamping down on politicians indulging in threatening languages must be nib at the bud	3000	1.5693	.62074	3.00	
					Std. Deviation Minimum Maximum

By ensuring that adequate penalty by INEC are imposed on political parties indulging in the use of hate speeches may also check election violence.	3000	1.7027	.69456	3.00	.73108	1.00	3.00
					.56789	1.00	3.00

Friedman Test

Ranks

	Mean Rank
Hate speech should be resisted by political parties and same be entrenched in the electoral acts	3.17
Some political parties deploy propaganda as a means and rivalry devices during campaigns	2.77
An intense magnitude of threatening languages before and during elections are capable of scaring away the electorates from the polling boots.	3.02
The ability of electoral body to set up monitoring committee in clamping down on politicians indulging in threatening languages must be nib at the bud	2.88
By ensuring that adequate penalty by INEC are imposed on political parties indulging in the use of hate speeches may also check election violence.	3.17

Test Statistics^a

N	3000
Chi-Square	464.583
Df	4
Asymp. Sig.	.000

a. Friedman Test

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